

Beyond the Breakup: Measuring Marital Dysfunction and Mental Health in Divorcees

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Abstract:

Despite socio-economic development, mental state of divorcees has still been an area of concern. This study investigates obstacles in marriage and its relationship with the mental health of divorcees. Data was collected from a sample of 75 male divorcees and 161 female divorcees (Total = 236) from Kolhapur, Sangli, Solapur, Pune (Districts of Maharashtra state, India). Obstacles in marriage scale was correlated with mental health. The findings of the study showed a significant but weak negative correlation between obstacles in marriage and mental health of divorcees. No gender and region wise difference was noted on obstacles in marriage. Mental health scores of divorcees from Sangli and Solapur were significantly lower than divorcees from Kolhapur and Pune. The study implies that obstacles in marriage may not be that harmful from the mental health point of view. The locality and social environment seem to be crucial, which calls for customised interventions for young divorcees.

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